

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies: United States of America (USA)

Version 1.0

**International
Science Council**

Author(s):

Meredith P. Goins
University of Tennessee, Knoxville
World Data System International Program Office
ORCID:0000-0002-0575-6240

This work is supported by a cooperative agreement (DE-SC0021915) under the U.S. Department of Energy Office of Science

About the World Data System:

Founded in 2008, the World Data System (WDS) is an affiliated body of the International Science Council (ISC). Its mission is to enhance the capabilities, impact, and sustainability of its member repositories and data services by fostering trusted communities of scientific data repositories. The WDS also aims to strengthen the entire lifecycle of data management, ensuring that high-quality data supports first-class research output. Additionally, it advocates for accessible data along with transparent and reproducible science.

<https://www.worlddatasystem.org/>

Suggested Citation: Goins, Meredith, Scientific Data Repository - related Policies: United States of America (USA). Knoxville, TN: World Data System International Program Office, October 2024 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13891155>

Table of Contents

Introduction.....1
Acronyms.....1
Scientific Data Repository-related Policies.....2
Bibliography.....3

Acronyms

HELIOS	Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship
JES	Joint Explanatory Statement
NSTC	National Science and Technology Council
OSTP	White House Office of Science and Technology Policy
OA	Open Access
PLOS	Public Library of Science
SOS	Subcommittee on Open Science
WDS	World Data System

Introduction

The World Data System (WDS) Policy Series reviews country-specific policies related to the governance of scientific data repositories at the national level. Documenting these policies comprehensively is critical to fostering global collaborations and advancing science for the common good.

To this end, WDS is committed to maintaining and continually updating a list of national Open Science policies pertaining to data repositories. Additionally, WDS will host periodic webinars featuring experts from multiple countries to discuss their unique perspectives on Open Science Policies and how they impact data repositories. These sessions aim to inform researchers and policymakers on how to navigate international policy landscapes effectively.

In developing this Open Science Policy Series, WDS's goal is to create avenues for sharing knowledge and enhancing global scientific collaboration efforts. Ultimately, we hope this approach will promote transparency and ensure that science continues to work towards the common good by leveraging diverse international expertise. Note that the papers in this series will continually be updated with new and emerging information as it becomes available. The World Data System welcomes your input on these documents, including textual updates, references, policy suggestions, and link corrections, by emailing wds-ipo@utk.edu.

Scientific Data Repository-related Policies

Scientific data repository-related policies specific to the USA include:

1. Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research

<https://doi.org/10.5479/10088/113528>

This short but impactful guidance was Issued in April 2022 by the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy's (OSTP) National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) Subcommittee on Open Science (SOS). All Federal agencies came to a consensus on what characteristics "all agencies could incorporate into the instructions they provide to the research community for selecting data repositories." (p. 1)

While not exhaustive, combining data characteristics under the three themes of organizational infrastructure, digital object management, and technology incorporates additional characteristics, as seen in Table 1 (pp. 4-5). Table 2 (p. 6) lists considerations for data repositories storing human data, including ethical and security considerations.

2. Updated Report to the U.S. Congress on Financing Mechanism for Open Access Publishing of Federally Funded Research

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/2024-Report-to-Appropriations-Committee-on-Scholarly-Publishing-and-Public-Access-Implementation.pdf>

This report was released by OSTP in response to the Joint Explanatory Statement (JES) accompanying Division C of the Consolidated Appropriations Act, 2024 (P.L. 118-42). It shares updates on the coordination of U.S. Government Agency Public Access Policies, business models associated with peer-reviewed scholarly publications, feeds paid by researchers, impacts on federal research investments, and how to advance research integrity with a further look at trends in peer review.

Although this focuses on open publishing, data repositories and scientific data are a part of the publication cycle and are included in the cost of publication and data sharing expenses through the different Open Access (OA) models (Green, Gold, Bronze, Hybrid, etc.) and how data can be shared.

The promotion of research integrity and the connection to scientific data management and sharing is mentioned (p. 20), and a helpful figure on the percentage of PLOS articles with associated data available in a data repository from 2018-2023 (Figure 9, p. 25). As an adjacent conversation, a brief discussion on organizations working to promote research assessment openly and responsibly for both publications and data, such as Make Data Count and the Higher Education Leadership Initiative for Open Scholarship (HELIOS), were mentioned. The final section focuses on peer review and the challenges that continue in these efforts.

Bibliography

The National Science and Technology Council, Desirable Characteristics of Data Repositories for Federally Funded Research, 2022, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5479/10088/113528> Accessed 1 July 2024.

OSTP. (2024). Updated Report to the U.S. Congress on Financing Mechanisms for Open Access Publishing of Federally Funded Research. Office of Science and Technology Policy, Washington, DC, USA. <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/2024-Report-to-Appropriations-Committee-on-Scholarly-Publishing-and-Public-Access-Implementation.pdf> Accessed 1 July 2024.

World Data System International Program Office

1345 Circle Park Drive
Communications Building
Knoxville, TN 37996-0341
01-865-974-2156

Email: wds-ipo@utk.edu
Website: worlddatasystem.org
Instagram: [@wds_ipo](https://www.instagram.com/wds_ipo)
LinkedIn: [@company/world-data-system](https://www.linkedin.com/company/world-data-system)
X (formerly Twitter): [@ISC_WDS](https://twitter.com/ISC_WDS)
Vimeo: [@worlddatasystem](https://vimeo.com/worlddatasystem)

**International
Science Council**